

ELECTRIC ENERGY EXTRACTION FROM MECHANICAL ENERGY**U.T.Berdiyev**

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Abstract. At present, there are many ways to generate electricity. Including: solar panels, wind turbines, hydroelectric power plants, nuclear power plants and internal combustion generators. A special part of our project is the extraction of electric current from mechanical energy.

Keywords: Car, suspension bridge, snowmobile, tires, conission-gearbox, shafts, electric car, batteries.

ИЗВЛЕЧЕНИЕ ЭЛЕКТРИЧЕСКОЙ ЭНЕРГИИ ИЗ МЕХАНИЧЕСКОЙ ЭНЕРГИИ

Аннотация. В настоящее время существует множество способов получения электроэнергии. В том числе: солнечные панели, ветрогенераторы, ГЭС, атомные электростанции и генераторы внутреннего сгорания. Особая часть нашего проекта — извлечение электрического тока из механической энергии.

Ключевые слова: Автомобиль, подвесной мост, снегоход, шины, кониссимон-редуктор, валы, электромобиль, аккумуляторы.

Log in:

Demand for electric energy is increasing from year to year. By now, even aftamabillars are driven by the energy of the electorate. This is beneficial for the ecological environment, but the electricity consumes energy in a wide way.

This is because cars are powered by batteries of much higher voltage. The main essence of our project is to get energy from the mechanical movement of a car, regardless of whether it is powered by electricity or fuel.

Our idea is mainly for rolling cars, buses and light trucks. First of all, we select the most of the car and mark its centerpiece. On our designated part, we place our cone gearbox transmitting mechanical motion on the shaft part of our electro dividate (see our point 7 in the project figure). In the next process, we pass shafts from our cone gearbox to the car tire and harden it into our cardan (we look at points 5-6 in the project figure). In the next process, we pass a shaft from our centrifugal cardan to our rotating bubble by touching the tire (look at our points 3-4-8 in the project picture). This tire gives us the formation of our mechanical motion.

Project photo

In our next process, the movement is transmitted from the car tire to the balloons, and we pass the shaft from our balloons to the shaft, from the shaft to the centrifugal cardan, and from there to our cone gearbox. We install a shaft to transmit the mechanical energy generated in our reducer to our electric dividate (Look at our point 1 in the project figure).

We place our electric motor in the car housing. With an electro dividate we install a tros vall in the middle part of our cone gearbox. It gives us the function of an implementer. Even when our machine is patched, it provides us with continuous mechanical energy. In the next process, we install the chargers of our electric dividate in the trunk of our car and install it so that we take away our batteries for charging. This is because it ensures that we install another battery when our battery is full.

Conclusion:

By doing this, we can obtain energy through an automobile, that is, we use the energy we receive from it to drive the car, to drive buildings, and to charge other electrical equipment. This will give us a lot of comfort and allow us to keep going.

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